

Lava flow mapping using COSMO-SkyMED imagery during the May 2023 Nyamulagira eruption

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In this report, an analysis of the changes that occurred over Mount Nyamulagira during the 2023 May eruption is undertaken to detect and evaluate the lava flow evolution.

According to <https://volcano.si.edu/showreport.cfm?wvar=GVP.WVAR20230517-223020>, lava flows began moving into the N and NW parts of the crater beginning on 9 May, towards the low point of the crater rim. The lava continued to erupt from vents during 17-23 May.

For this analysis, a time series of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) COSMO-SkyMED (CSK) imagery is used. The change detection methodology is based on the SAR intensity difference between two images collected before and after the event.

Images are in stripmap mode, HH polarization, 2.25m x 2.25m resolution on the ground, and with ascending orbit.

The table shows the processed CSK intensity images:

a) 28 April 2023	
b) 13 May 2023	

c) 14 May 2023

d) 22 May 2023

e) 30 May 2023

f) 15 June 2023

From the images above the evolution of the SAR signal intensity over the period can be appreciated in and around the Nyamulagira crater.

In this case, the presence of a lava flow should be represented by a lighter shade of gray (an increase of SAR signal backscattering) in the successive intensity image dates.

A visual comparison between (a) (28 April) and (b) (13 May) shows that changes inside the caldera have occurred, with a general increase of the intensity inside the crater. It can be also noted a movement of the lava flow into the NW part of the crater.

No changes are appreciated between 13 May (b) and 14 May (c).

Instead, large differences are visible between 14 May (c) and 22 May (d) due to the eruption onset. In particular, the lava flow covered the N and SW parts of the crater and it started to flow out in the W flank. In particular, the extent of the new lava coverage towards the N can be appreciated by the reduction in the size of the dark area adjacent to the N rim.

The visual comparison between (d) (22 May) and (e) (30 May) shows that the lava flow continues to flow out in the W flank that, even in this case, can be appreciated by a reduction of the dark area close to the W flank.

The visual comparison between (a) (30 May) and (b) (15 June) shows that no changes can be appreciated. The two images appear pretty similar.

To better identify these changes, a change detection approach based on the intensity difference is applied to each pair of contiguous CSK images [1]:

$$i_{CD} = \frac{i_1 - i_2}{i_1 + i_2}$$

where i_1 and i_2 are the intensity CSK images collected at two different times.

Results are shown in Figure 1 which confirms the visual intensity analysis previously undertaken. The changes associated with the lava flow are represented by dark pixels. The flank lava flow extension is manually traced and shown as a red polygon.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

Figure 1 – Change detection maps between a) 28 April and 13 May; b) 13 May and 14 May; c) 14 May and 22 May; d) 22 May and 30 May; and e) 30 May and 15 June. The changes associated with the lava flow are represented by dark pixels. The W flank lava flow pattern evident in c) (22 May) and d) (30 May) is shown by a red polygon in f) and g), respectively.

To evaluate the total changes that occurred since the lava started to flow out of the caldera until its end, the change detection approach is applied to a pair of imagery collected on 28 April and 15 June 2023. The result is shown in Figure 2 where the changes associated with the lava flow are shown as dark pixels. The flank lava flow extension is manually traced and shown as a red polygon.

Figure 2 – Change detection map between 28 April and 15 June (a). The changes associated with the lava flow are represented by dark pixels. The W flank lava flow pattern is manually traced and shown by a red polygon in b).

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Stramondo, C. Bignami, M. Chini, N. Pierdicca, e A. Tertulliani, «Satellite radar and optical remote sensing for earthquake damage detection: results from different case studies», *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 27, fasc. 20, pp. 4433–4447, ott. 2006, doi: [10.1080/01431160600675895](https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160600675895)